

EVORoads

DIGITAL TWIN AND SMART ROAD EQUIPMENT V1

Project deliverable D3.1

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

Acronym	Meaning
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AOI	Automated Optical Inspection
API	Application Programming Interface
ASAP	As Soon As Possible
B2B	Business-to-business
B2C	Business-to-Consumer
CAM	Cooperative Awareness Message
CPU	Central Processing Unit
DENM	Decentralised Environmental Notification Message
DT	Digital Twin
EC	European Commission
GA	Grant Agreement
IoT	Internet of Things
IP67	Ingress Protection 67
IME	In-Mold Electronics
ISWB	Individual Smart Warning Beacons
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
KoM	Kick-off Meeting
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LED	Light Emitting Diode
LoRa	Long Range
ML	Machine Learning
NDT	Network Digital Twin
OBU	On Board Unit

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PCB	Printed Circuit Board
PMMA	Polymethyl methacrylate
REST	REpresentational State Transfer
RSU	Road Side Unit
UV	Ultraviolet
VRU	Vulnerable Road User
V2X	Vehicle to Everything
WP	Work Package

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PROJECT EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The EC-funded project EvoRoads (Evolutionary Solutions for Realising a Holistic Safe System Approach for All Road Users) is committed to advancing the European Union's Vision Zero initiative by implementing a comprehensive framework that integrates innovative models, tools, and services for data-driven safety assessments.

The project focuses on developing of a connectivity platform that digitalises transport infrastructure assets while enabling the seamless integration of safety assessment services. By leveraging advanced artificial intelligence, EvoRoads analyses infrastructure monitoring data at various geospatial levels, enabling proactive risk warnings and supporting road operators in managing maintenance more effectively, enhancing safety and operational efficiency. It also defines safety criteria and quantification methods for key performance indicators (KPIs) to monitor safety performance as part of the "Safe System" approach.

The results are developed alongside five axes: (1) an **Evolutionary Safety Assessment Framework** setting the basis by defining how to measure road safety in a multilayered catalogue; (2) a **Road Asset & Safety Management Digital Twin** collecting and distributing safety data; (3) **Advanced Monitoring Safety Systems** that leverage data to provide infrastructure owners with clear insights into the safety levels of their roads; (4) **Proactive Safety Warning Systems** ensuring that critical safety issues are raised pro-actively and in real-time to prevent safety hazards; and finally, all these results are combined in (5) **Solutions Integration, Augmentation and Impact Assessment tools and products** allowing for take-up of the results in the wider market. These axes converge into a **Safe Mobility Data Space** where all data related to EvoRoads' safety criteria and solutions are combined.

EvoRoads' methodologies and technologies will be validated in four Living Labs (LLs) addressing diverse road user scenarios across urban and rural environments to ensure broad applicability and effectiveness. EvoRoads LLs are situated in **Spain** (focusing on **Hazard-aware assets for better infrastructure safety level for existing and future roads users**), **Italy** (focusing on **Dynamic Road infrastructure safety diagnosis enhanced by emerging vehicle and digital technologies**), **Latvia** (focusing on **Automated (advanced) low-cost infrastructure monitoring and diagnostics: road hot spots, bridges, tunnels**), and **Romania** (focusing on **Remote sensing and warning technologies for better infrastructure and road conditions**).

The EvoRoads project runs from May 2024 until April 2027. A scale-up event is foreseen towards the end of the project to allow for the wider market to consider EvoRoads' results and to help provide ways forward.

Social Media link:

For further information please visit evoroads-project.eu

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DELIVERABLE EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable introduces the first version of the EvoRoads Digital Twin and Smart Road Equipment solutions, representing a significant advancement toward the EU's Vision Zero goal of eliminating road fatalities by 2050. The document details two primary innovations: a Digital Twin platform for road infrastructure digitalization and cost-effective plastronics smart road equipment to enhance road safety signalling.

Digital Twin Platform: The EvoRoads Digital Twin integrates and manages all the data of the smart road infrastructure, built on a Kafka¹-based message broker architecture that enables real-time data collection, processing, and distribution across the platform. The system supports multiple deployment architectures, with the initial implementation following a single shared infrastructure among all pilots for efficient data sharing. Key features include:

- Standardised application programming interfaces (APIs) for seamless data flow creation and management with user-specific access control
- Historical database integration for long-term data retention and in-depth analytics
- Seamless integration with Artificial Intelligence (AI) tools and pilot sites for adaptive safety management
- Network Digital Twin capabilities for V2X connectivity analysis leveraging innovative sampling techniques

Plastronic Smart Road Equipment: The project uses plastronic technology for smart guardrail lighting, where electronics are fully embedded in injection-moulded plastic housing during manufacturing. This approach ensures enhanced durability and environmental protection while allowing cost-effective mass production. The system architecture consists of:

- Individual Smart Warning Beacons with IP67 waterproofing and minimal maintenance requirements
- Local Hubs managing power distribution, control logic, and LoRa communication
- Central Nodes providing Internet connectivity and Digital Twin integration
- Hierarchical communication using LoRa mesh networking for extended coverage in rural environments

The Digital Twin serves as the primary data input mechanism for AI models and services responsible for analysing real-time road traffic conditions and patterns. The system facilitates the development of comprehensive safety solutions while providing seamless integration with downstream analytical processes.

The Network Digital Twin provides critical infrastructure assessment capabilities by delivering real-time estimation of Infrastructure Safety Assessment and Design (ISAD) levels across road networks while continuously monitoring Vehicle-to-Everything (V2X) connectivity parameters.

Advanced plastronics equipment deployment enables direct driver communication through embedded road infrastructure integration suitable for both urban and rural environments. This technology facilitates real-time signal transmission to road users and seamlessly integrates with service outputs to provide immediate communication capabilities. The plastronics equipment receives outputs from various services that benefit road infrastructure by communicating information directly with drivers, creating an immediate response mechanism for safety-critical situations.

The integration with AI tools from Work Package 2 (WP2) completes the communication chain by enabling bi-directional information flow between infrastructure and road users. This enhanced connectivity delivers intelligent service delivery to both individual road actors and infrastructure management teams while supporting automated hazard detection and

¹ <https://kafka.apache.org/>
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response systems throughout the network. The resulting integrated technological framework establishes a complete end-to-end solution for intelligent road safety management, providing infrastructure managers with comprehensive monitoring capabilities while delivering real-time safety information directly to road users through advanced communication channels.

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1 INTRODUCTION

The objective of this deliverable is to present the initial results of the activities that have been carried out in Task 3.1 – Safe Roads: Digitalised ecosystem for transport infrastructure and operations and Task 3.2 – Safe Road Equipment: Cost effective & smart equipment for road safety. The deliverable type is “DEM — Demonstrator, pilot, prototype” so the results listed in this document are focused on the design and implementation of the presented solutions.

The deliverable contains the work done on two main components the **Digital Twin platform** (T3.1) and the **Plastronic Smart Road Equipment** (T3.2) during this first round of development; D3.3 will then build on D3.1 and D3.2 to showcase the work done in WP3 during the whole project.

The Digital Twin Platform is a scalable way to collect data flows coming from the field and make them available for third parties who need to use them. This will be useful both for partners that develop AI tools and need to test them in a real world scenario, and for anyone needing to perform analysis on the data coming from the Pilots.

Furthermore, the Digital Twin can provide data from different Pilots together in a transparent way, increasing the data available for developers without increasing the complexity on their side: this is possible because T2.1 and T3.1 cooperate to guarantee a correct preprocessing of the data in a common data schema. Data from the Pilot sites will be sent to the **Data Acquisition Platform** (T2.1), that will process it to map it in a common format and then forward it to the Digital Twin. A user can use the Dashboard (T1.5) both to request data from the Digital Twin and to request AI model execution (WP2). This software architecture will be explained in detail in deliverables D1.3 and D1.4, that focus on the whole integrated platform.

The Plastronics Smart Road Equipment leverages plastronics technology to create cost-effective and durable smart warning beacons that integrate electronics directly into injection-moulded plastic components. This equipment is designed to send different programmable LED signals to road actors, signalling different dangerous events. The LoRa long-range communication allows to dynamically program the LED patterns. This technology will be tested mainly in the IDIADA Santa Oliva test track with five warning beacons along a 100-meter section to demonstrate coordinated signalling capabilities.

1.1 MAPPING EVOROADS OUTPUTS

Table 1: Adherence to EvoRoads GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions

EVOROADS GA COMPONENT TITLE	EVOROADS GA COMPONENT OUTLINE	RESPECTIVE DOCUMENT CHAPTER(S)	JUSTIFICATION
DELIVERABLE			
D3.1 - Digital Twin and smart road equipment V1	The first release of the digitalised ecosystem for the cyberphysical infrastructure and operations, together with the smart equipment for road safety	Chapters 2,3,4	Chapter 2 describes the first implementation of the Digital Twin in the EvoRoads Platform. Chapter 3 shows the first iteration of the work on economic and durable road equipment to provide important safety information to the road users.

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Chapter 4 presents a final set of solutions from Chapter 2 and 3 for each of the pilots taking into account the feasibility of implementation.

TASKS

T3.1	<p>This task will design the digitalised ecosystem centred around road safety. This will involve the development of a Digital Twin (DT) that integrates several different (static and dynamic) road attributes aggregating data from various sources, providing dedicated APIs to facilitate the analysis of data.</p>	Chapter 2	<p>Section 2.1 defines what a Digital Twin is in the scope of the EvoRoads project.</p> <p>Section 2.2 provides a list of features exposed from the Digital Twin and an explanation of each one of them.</p> <p>Section 2.3 maps the interactions of the DT with the other components of the EvoRoads projects.</p> <p>Section 2.4 describes the future implementation of the Network Digital Twin.</p>
T3.2	<p>This task includes the development of dynamic signage using Plastronics, a low-cost high-throughput technology, allowing the communication of dynamic safety warnings to road users.</p>	Chapter 3	<p>Section 3.1 introduces the plastronics-based smart warning beacon concept and its relevance for road safety.</p> <p>Section 3.2 describes the three-level architecture: ISWB, Local Hub, and Central Node, and their roles in the system.</p> <p>Section 3.3 details the design and manufacturing process of the ISWB, including materials and assembly steps.</p> <p>Section 3.4 explains the warning pattern logic, including morse code alerts and sequential activation for behavioural nudging.</p>

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			<p>Section 3.5 outlines the power supply, battery management, and communication infrastructure for the beacon system.</p> <p>Section 3.6 summarises how the system exchanges data with the Digital Twin and external sources for monitoring and control.</p> <p>Section 3.7 presents the IDIADA pilot deployment, setup, and main technical testing outcomes.</p>
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1.2 DELIVERABLE OVERVIEW AND REPORT STRUCTURE

D3.1 - Digital Twin and smart road equipment V1 aims to provide both software and hardware solutions to increase road safety at the pilot sites. These solutions will be derived from the results of Tasks 3.1 and 3.2. The focus is on addressing safety issues in problematic areas identified at one or more of the pilot sites, through various strategies:

- Digital Twin as a tool to ease the consumption of road data (Task 3.1)
- Plastronics equipment, as a cost effective and durable tool to communicate with road users (Task 3.2)

The proposed solutions serve as enablers for potential implementation during the first and/or second demonstration phases at one or more pilot sites. A final set of solutions to be implemented is determined based on the outputs of the pilots during the first demonstrations.

The deliverable is structured as follows:

- Chapter 2 covers the Digital Twin (DT) in the EvoRoads project: it starts with a brief description of the concept of Digital Twin (analysing some other projects that used this technology in similar scenario) then focuses on the technical description of the work done in T3.1; it ends with a short demonstration of what has been developed in this first iteration of development.
- Chapter 3 describes the Plastronics equipment developed in T3.2: it starts with a summary on the different technologies available to convey information to the drivers, describing pros and cons, and then explains how this type of technology can be used to increase the road safety.
- Chapter 4 summarises the contents of the Deliverable, providing suggestions to the Pilot sites that will use these technologies and listing the next steps to be performed in T3.1 and T3.2.

1.3 AI ACT COMPLIANCE IN THE EVORoads PROJECT

AI Act Compliance in the EvoRoads project

To guarantee the responsible development and use of AI, the European Union has defined the concept of Trustworthy AI based on three fundamental pillars: compliance with existing laws and regulations (Lawful), adherence to fundamental human values (Ethical) and technical security and resilience against risks (Robust). As outlined in the **Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI**¹, these principles have been translated into practical requirements, such as transparency, human oversight, data protection, and fairness.

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The **AI Act**² is a European regulation that integrates the Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI into a binding regulatory framework, establishing concrete rules, classifying AI-based systems, and imposing stringent requirements for high-risk applications. The regulation introduces a risk-based classification system for AI-based systems, dividing them into four main categories:

- **Unacceptable risk:** Prohibited systems, such as those employing subliminal manipulative techniques or social scoring;
- **High risk:** Applications impacting critical sectors (e.g., healthcare, infrastructure, mobility) that are subject to strict compliance requirements;
- **Limited risk:** Systems that require transparency obligations, such as chatbots or deepfakes;
- **Minimal risk:** Unregulated systems, such as spam filters or AI-powered video games.

The AI Act seeks to balance technological innovation with the protection of fundamental rights, promoting the responsible use of AI. It includes human oversight, data security, and non-discrimination provisions while supporting AI-based research and development in strategic sectors.

EvoRoads Project is committed to fully complying with the EU AI Act, its core principles, and the Trustworthy AI criteria, ensuring that all developed AI-based technologies are lawful, ethical, robust, and respectful of human rights and values.

The EvoRoads project involves multiple entities, meaning any subject (company, individual, or public body) engaged in developing, distributing, or using an AI-based system. Depending on their role, each entity has specific obligations and responsibilities to ensure compliance with European AI regulations. The key entities involved in the EvoRoads Project include:

- **Provider:** A company, public entity, or individual that develops an AI-based system or a general-purpose AI model and places it on the market or into service under its own name or brand;
- **Deployer:** Any entity using an AI system under its authority (e.g., companies, public bodies), except for personal, non-professional use.

To correctly classify the role of each EvoRoads beneficiary and the characteristics of the AI-based systems being developed, used, or distributed, the project will leverage the **EU AI Act Compliance Checker**³.

By answering a series of questions, this tool will support EvoRoads beneficiaries in identifying the risk level of EvoRoads AI-based system and being informed about specific articles of the AI Act to be considered to be fully compliant with trustworthy AI principles. The results provided by the tool will be documented in project deliverables dedicated to the EvoRoads AI-based solutions.

By leveraging the EU AI Act Compliance Checker, the EvoRoads project will ensure full compliance with European AI regulations, fostering the development and adoption of safe, ethical, and reliable AI-based systems in road transport.

2 SAFE ROADS: DIGITALISED ECOSYSTEM FOR TRANSPORT INFRASTRUCTURE AND OPERATIONS

The spread of Internet of Things (IoT) devices in urban areas and the steadily increasing number of connected road users make available large volumes of data that can be exploited to offer a large variety of innovative services aiming at improving the mobility experience, increasing the road safety, or, if historical data collection is available, planning the development of the city effectively.

Data gathering and delivering is a critical aspect, and an effective solution must be provided since it is necessary to provide scalability and to make easily accessible relevant data to end users. The emerging concept of Digital Twins (DTs) has been leveraged in the context of smart cities to achieve these objectives.

A DT provides the means to collect data from a heterogeneous set of sources, store them, and make them available to data-driven digital services. The concept of DTs is widely used in the industry 4.0 vertical and the healthcare sector. In the smart city topic context, the DT typically provides digital information on the road infrastructure and, potentially, real-time status information such as traffic lights status or traffic conditions.

The Snap4City Smart City Digital Twin⁽⁴⁵⁾ framework is a solution for urban areas' DT that considers both static information, such as road networks and urban infrastructure, and inputs from IoT devices and sensors that monitor information in real-time such as traffic and air quality. The information contained in the DT can be accessed through 3D web interfaces enabling stakeholders and citizens to transparently access the data for participating in decision-making. This framework is used in several locations and the paper reports results and insights for the city of Florence (Italy), and Helsinki (Finland).

The Digital Twin of the city of Sydney⁽⁴⁶⁾ integrates data coming live from different sources with periodic updates and data provided by offline datasets that have been offline collected. This study shows how data integrated in a Digital Twin can be successfully leveraged using machine learning techniques, especially when try to increase the road safety.

The METACITIES project⁽⁴⁷⁾ showcases how a Digital Twin has a central role in creating an accurate replica of several mobility aspects in the city of Patras. The DT in this study has been used to address urban transportation challenges through three use cases: Smart Parking, Environmental Behaviour Analysis, and Emergency Management.

Drawing from these precedents, the approach used takes inspiration from the success factors identified in these implementations, particularly the real-time data integration capabilities demonstrated by Snap4City. EvoRoads' DT supports also the integration with AI tools and is designed with a more complex architecture supporting scalability and low latency.

2.1 DESCRIPTION OF THE DIGITAL TWIN

In EvoRoads, the Digital Twin is a core component, allowing communication between different tasks and pilots. This component will act as a common communication bus between different actors. The Digital Twin creates a unified data ecosystem that enables seamless information exchange across the entire platform.

Built around a Kafka-based message broker, the system provides standardised APIs for data flow creation and management, with each dataflow automatically generating dedicated Kafka topics for secure, user-specific access. The architecture includes a historical database component for long-term data retention and analysis, supporting retrospective queries and pattern identification.

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For our initial implementation, a single shared infrastructure model will be deployed, offering simplicity and efficient data sharing capabilities while maintaining the flexibility to evolve toward a more sophisticated layered architecture as project requirements mature.

2.1.1 ARCHITECTURAL COMPONENTS

The Digital Twin architecture is composed of several components, each serving specific functions.

2.1.1.1 KAFKA DATA BUS

Apache Kafka is a publish-subscribe message broker, designed for high-throughput and low latency data streaming. In the scope of EvoRoads, it serves as a central messaging backbone, shared with the data acquisition platform in Task 2.1. Kafka is by design horizontally scalable, and implements message persistence and replication, this will allow to prevent data loss and have more stability in a shared platform.

2.1.1.2 DIGITAL TWIN APIS

The Digital Twin APIs allow programmatic interfaces to interact with the platform and manage dataflows. These RESTful APIs allow users to create, modify and delete dataflows; each dataflow is accessible only to the user who generates it. Swagger² documentation is available for all the endpoints, both as a guide provided for users and as an /UI endpoint to read the definition of the APIs.

To generate dataflow, the APIs communicate with the Kafka broker using the ksqlDB³ APIs; ksqlDB is a technology that allows to access and perform operations on real time Kafka messages using a SQL-line syntax.

2.1.1.3 HISTORICAL DATABASE

The historical database is deployed to store the message history for retrospective analysis. The Kafka broker store messages only for a short period of time (Retention time) and then deletes them, so a separate database is required to store all the messages going into the Digital Twin from the pilots. The database chosen is CouchDB⁴, a document-oriented database. Being a noSQL database, it allows for heterogenous and flexibles data schemas across the project. Another possible choice available was MongoDB⁵, but we discarded it due to its limiting licence policy. CouchDB, instead, is provided under an Apache 2.0 license.

2.1.1.4 AUTHENTICATION & AUTHORIZATION

This layer manages user identity verification and access control. It is implemented using Keycloak⁶ as Identity provider and Apache APISIX⁷ to enforce access control rules on the API endpoints and on the data resources. Both these products are provided with Apache 2.0 License, that allows a "business-friendly" approach without the need to share the code derived by their use. Components may change during the lifecycle of the project, as we are evaluating the possibility of to use HAProxy⁸ as reverse-proxy instead of APISIX, but the high-level functionality from the design will remain the same.

² <https://swagger.io/>

³ <https://docs.confluent.io/platform/current/ksqldb/overview.html>

⁴ <https://couchdb.apache.org/>

⁵ <https://www.mongodb.com/>

⁶ <https://www.keycloak.org/>

⁷ <https://apisix.apache.org/>

⁸ <https://www.haproxy.com/>

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2.1.2 DEPLOYMENT ARCHITECTURE

In the scope of a multi pilot project as EvoRoads, we identified three possible deployment architectures for this common data infrastructure.

2.1.2.1 PROPOSAL 1: SINGLE SHARED INFRASTRUCTURE

This approach implements a centralised deployment model where all pilots publish data to a singular Digital Twin instance. Access control is implemented at API level with granular permission settings. Hardware resources are shared across all pilots.

The main advantage of this architecture is the simplicity: one single deployment, centralised data governance, simplified access for cross-pilot collaboration and collaboration between pilots and partners developing AI tools.

There are several challenges in this scenario: on the management side the challenges are the management of the shared infrastructure and the compliance to local data sharing policies that may not allow all the data from a pilot site to be shared outside the country in which was generated. On the technical side, there could be latency and scalability issues: having a central platform creates a single bottleneck if a lot of data is published, furthermore a user will need to retrieve data from the central platform even the publisher is in the same country or region, increasing latency.

Figure 1: First possible architecture of DT interactions with Pilots and Users

2.1.2.2 PROPOSAL 2: DISTRIBUTED PARTNER DEPLOYMENTS

This decentralised approach implements independent Digital Twin deployments for each pilot. Each pilot will own its own independent Digital Twin, and the data published in it.

The main advantages of this architecture are the real-time performance and the compliance to local data sharing policies: since the broker is physically located near the data source, is easy to provide real-time feedback; and data will not leave the pilot site.

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On the other hand, in this scenario the collaboration between different pilots as well as between pilots and AI tool providers will be more complicated, and some additional mechanisms to share data among partners should be implemented.

Figure 2: Second possible architecture of the DT interactions with Pilots and Users

2.1.2.3 PROPOSAL 3: LAYERED PLATFORM

This hybrid approach implements a two-tier architecture with local Digital Twins for direct pilot operations and a common layer for shared, non-sensitive data access. In the first layer each pilot will deploy its own Digital Twin, while the second layer will be a shared platform Digital Twin. In the first layer, data sources will publish all the data they produce, and pilot data subscribers can receive anything they need for their demonstrators; in the second layer, data sources will send only non-sensitive data, that can then be received by any partner in the project.

The main advantage of this solution is the flexibility, as it combines the benefits of both centralised and distributed approaches: low latency within the pilots, ease the data sharing between partners, privacy protection for sensitive data.

On the other hand, this solution has a complicated implementation that required coordination between the layers and the partners. This adds some operational overload in the monitoring and maintenance of the infrastructure

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Figure 3: Third possible architecture of the DT interactions with Pilots and Users

2.1.2.4 CHOSEN DEPLOYMENT

For the first development iteration of the EvoRoads Digital Twin, we will implement a hybrid solution between Proposal 1 and Proposal 3: there are a shared Data Acquisition Platform and Digital Twin, but they will be used mainly for processed data, while raw data will be processed inside the Pilots' local infrastructure. The Pilots partially implement their own local data plane. This decision enables us to develop rapidly a functional foundation and to maintain the data sharing capabilities between all partners.

Following the first demonstrator round in WP4, we will evaluate pilot site's feedback, and we will determine whether to maintain this architecture or to migrate to the more complex approach described in the Proposal 3.

2.2 API SPECIFICATION

The APIs allow to create, manage and delete dataflow. To access these endpoints, the user should be authenticated from the Authentication and Authorization component.

The following endpoints are used to provide access to real-time data. In the second iteration of the Digital Twin development will be implemented endpoints to consume historical dataflows; these endpoints will match the schema of the real-time ones, adding `start_time` and `end_time` as parameters in the dataflow creation.

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2.2.1 LIST USER DATAFLOWS

GET /topics: this endpoint returns the list of active dataflows (and Kafka topics) currently associated to the user performing the request.

Figure 4: Sequence diagram of GET /topics

2.2.2 CREATE NEW DATAFLOW

POST /topics: this endpoint requires as body parameters a set of filters regarding the data that needs to be consumed (i.e. the type of data, the format, the location, other attributes in the body of the message, etc.). The endpoint will connect to Kafka through the KSQL API and generate a Kafka topic containing only the messages that match the requirements, then will return the topic name to the user.

Figure 5: Sequence diagram of POST /topic

2.2.3 INSPECT DATAFLOW

GET /topic/<topicname>: this endpoint will return the query that generated a topic, provided the name by the user.

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Figure 6: Sequence diagram of GET /topic/<topicname>

2.2.4 DELETE DATAFLOW

DELETE /topic/<topicname>: this endpoint will delete the topic.

Figure 7: Sequence diagram of DELETE /topic/<topicname>

2.3 INTEGRATION WITH OTHER COMPONENTS IN THE PLATFORM

2.3.1 INTEGRATION WITH THE PILOTS

The Digital Twin (T3.1) is connected to the pilot sites (T4.2, T4.3, T4.4 and T4.5) through the Data Acquisition Platform (T2.1), with which it shares the Kafka broker. The Data Acquisition Platform will merge data coming from the same Pilot, perform some preprocessing, if needed, and then forward it to the Digital Twin.

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To consume data from the Digital Twin, the pilots will need to create a dataflow using the REST APIs and then subscribe to the dataflow using Kafka.

The Digital Twin does not expose a user-friendly GUI for not technical users, but it is possible to provide a dashboard both the Kafka broker (akhq.io) and the APIs. A user-friendly GUI to interact with the data and AI models without the need for technical expertise is planned to be implemented in the scope of T1.5. This dashboard will allow to interact with the data without the need to implement code or API requests, so that not-technical users can retrieve the data shared by the pilots.

Figure 8: Schema of possible communication with other Tasks

2.3.2 INTEGRATION WITH AI TOOLS

The EvoRoads platform will be able to deploy function to estimate the road safety KPI receive from Task 1.3. These functions will take as input information store in the Digital Twin and result as a number some metrics about the road status.

Furthermore, users external to the EvoRoads platform should be able to use EvoRoads to launch the AI Models developed in the WP2 tasks on the data stored in the Digital Twin to receive some services. For this reason, between T1.5 and T3.1, it will be developed an AI Controller. This AI Controller will be able to translate a service request from a non-technical user into both a data request to the DT and an AI model request to run inference on the selected data.

In this section we have a proposal for the integration with both the AI tools and these KPIs; this solution is not yet implemented but will be the design for the next deployment in the task.

The proposed solution works as follows:

1. The user asks for a service to be deployed; this will trigger both a data request and a request for an AI model
2. The dashboard forwards the data request to Digital Twin
3. The Digital Twin instantiates the dataflow and responds with the user specific Kafka topic
4. The AI Controller connects to the chosen AI model, and forwards the dataflow from where to receive the data
5. The AI model subscribes to the dataflow and generates a result

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6. Results are forwarded to user via the Dashboard

Figure 9: Schema of possible interaction with Pilot, User and AI model

2.4 NETWORK DIGITAL TWIN

In the context of EvoRoads project, a Network Digital Twin solution (NDT) solution will be proposed for V2X connectivity analysis. However, achieving this objective in a scalable fashion is not straightforward. Indeed, frequent NDT synchronizations with the real V2X network creates scalability challenges given the inherent complexity of such networks (e.g. too large number of network entities, highly dynamic topologies, large volume of information per node or per network link), especially when detailed V2X network information must be continuously mirrored within the NDT.

The proposed NDT solution relies on network sampling to enable both selective and incremental data acquisition from the real communication network. Upon each network sampling phase, a *zoom-in/out* operation over the real communication network is performed, depending on whether more (*zoom-in*) or less (*zoom-out*) details need to be exposed for a specific segment (sample) of the real communication network. This solution is particularly useful when there is a need for saving network resources (bandwidth, memory, CPU, energy), while managing effectively the communication network (i.e. collect only the relevant network parameters). Additionally, this modular NDT generation also enables an incremental generation of the complete NDT, if necessary.

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The proposed NDT platform will comprise the following functional components:

- **V2X Env. Emulator:** It comprises various functionalities that simulate vehicle movements and associated traffic patterns. The emulator also includes the simulation of V2X networks, constraints, and data traffic patterns. The V2X Env. Emulator will be further refined based on inputs from the Spanish (T4.2) and Romanian (T4.5) pilots.
- **V2X Network Descriptor:** it generates fine-grained and real-time instance of the full emulated V2X network.
- **V2X Network Sample Generator:** It is responsible for generating V2X network samples based on predefined criteria, such as random sampling or selective/event-based network sampling. Multiple instances of a given V2X sample may be generated over a time period to ensure that the NDT counterpart remains valid (see the ‘Error Calculator’ component below).
- **ML Engine:** this engine will be used to predict future data traffic patterns within the V2X network. Leveraging historical and real-time data, the model learns from a range of V2X-specific features such as mobility patterns, vehicle density, and application-level message types (e.g., CAMs, DENMs). These predictions allow the NDT to proactively generate forward-looking representations of network behaviour, such as anticipated link congestion and fluctuations in data throughput.
- **Error Calculator:** This component calculates the difference between the latest instance of a given physical V2X network sample and the most recent predicted instance from its corresponding NDT counterpart (i.e., the last predicted NDT instance associated with that physical sample). If this difference exceeds a predefined threshold, a new instance of the physical V2X sample is generated and adopted as the current NDT image. Otherwise, the most recent predicted NDT instance continues to serve as the current representation of the physical V2X sample.

Within the framework of the EvoRoads project, an incremental implementation approach will be adopted. In the first iteration, a V2X sampling functionality will be developed, followed by the instantiation of the predicted V2X Network Digital Twin (NDT) using machine learning-based traffic prediction.

Figure 10: Schema of The Network Digital Twin

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2.5 DEMONSTRATION: EXAMPLE USAGE OF THE DT APIS

This section contains an example of how the user can use the APIs to receive real time data from the Digital Twin. The main steps are:

1. Login in the DT.
2. Create a dataflow, selecting some message filters.
3. Optional, check the creation of the topic.
4. Use Kafka to subscribe to the generated topic; the topic contains only the messages that match the filters from the step 2
5. Delete the topic

A video of this demonstrator can be found [here](#).

2.5.1 USER LOGIN

Figure 11: DT APIs, user login

2.5.2 TOPIC CREATION

Figure 12: DT APIs, topic creation

Figure 13: DT APIs, topic created

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2.5.3 ANALIZE A TOPIC

Figure 14: DT APIs, topic query

2.5.4 SUBSCRIBE TO THE KAFKA TOPIC

```

rrycbarm@rrycbarm-HP-ZBook:~/EvoRoads/DT_DEMO/python_clients$ python3 consumer.py EVOUSER_1000
/home/rrycbarm/EvoRoads/DT_DEMO/python_clients/consumer.py:58: DeprecationWarning: AvroConsumer has been deprecated. Use
AvroDeserializer instead.
  consumer = AvroConsumer(consumer_config)
Connected to Kafka cluster at localhost:9092
Schema Registry at http://localhost:8089
Subscribed to topic: EVOUSER_1000
Consumer group: python-avro-consumer-group
Starting from: latest
Waiting for messages... (Press Ctrl+C to stop)

Topic: EVOUSER_1000
Partition: 0, Offset: 22
Key: None
Value: {'COUNTRY': 'ITA', 'DATATYPE': 'CAM', 'PAYLOAD': '{"type": "CAM", "vehicleId": "5663", "speed": 73.19, "data": "kW
0F49uzHirBmjbWAlAqEeInWu5KblhzpwnZFHeUHHXkZz8aHgFbzE9jRARuMnDBfuFgYL4ne1y6WspnJ9065a5ndVUQDJkZVCt"}', 'TIMESTAMP': 17515
46380733}
Timestamp: 1751546380734 (CreateTime)
-----

```

Figure 15: DT APIs, Kafka consumer logs

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```

Partition: 0, Offset: 34
Key: None
Value: {'COUNTRY': 'ITA', 'DATATYPE': 'CAM', 'PAYLOAD': '{"type": "CAM", "vehicleId": "3119", "speed": 66.98, "data": "qPkJvLbLdS7w9u7FddLT9Zn5o2ew1qHh8AbjxBd7ddQCsJkYGYHd0XxjgFTawbrF6FCqhDMJVkVsgo58femjP3a5fXo7oEmEWh4"}', 'TIMESTAMP': 1751546393700}
Timestamp: 1751546393700 (CreateTime)
-----
Topic: EVOUSER_1000
Partition: 0, Offset: 35
Key: None
Value: {'COUNTRY': 'ITA', 'DATATYPE': 'CAM', 'PAYLOAD': '{"type": "CAM", "vehicleId": "6749", "speed": 76.77, "data": "2RTSwBPV5HJ6m1XNLMgti0aZwJwVz9bwjoksrURZfKpdAKuzY6NnwJgoYdcognCWKAiyGW2EbWm3987qizWvJoBMkLq6DJ9VZ4mt"}', 'TIMESTAMP': 1751546395134}
Timestamp: 1751546395134 (CreateTime)
-----
Topic: EVOUSER_1000
Partition: 0, Offset: 36
Key: None
Value: {'COUNTRY': 'ITA', 'DATATYPE': 'CAM', 'PAYLOAD': '{"type": "CAM", "vehicleId": "2437", "speed": 50.32, "data": "0bcZCpoTzxxUgsAuh1JcsM5ff7DuSpulBkknQB2Y0KHiiUu7ry5iAE7xkbWomzPBXXQNYzn1cbY8SuJs7jw28xFVZqtYy36p9hFy"}', 'TIMESTAMP': 1751546397299}
Timestamp: 1751546397299 (CreateTime)
-----

```

Figure 16: DT APIs, Kafka consumer logs

2.5.5 DELETE THE TOPIC

Figure 17: DT APIs, topic deletion

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Figure 18: DT APIs, topic deleted

3 SAFE ROAD EQUIPMENT – COST-EFFECTIVE & SMART GUARDRAIL LIGHTING USING PLASTRONICS

This section presents the EvoRoads approach to developing cost-effective smart road equipment based on plastronics technology for enhanced road safety. The solution focuses on innovative Individual Smart Warning Beacons (ISWBs) composed of smart plastic parts with integrated electronics and embedded components for realizing infrastructure-based solutions that can elicit desirable user behaviours. The development integrates cutting-edge manufacturing processes with advanced connectivity and Digital Twin platforms to deliver scalable, sustainable road safety solutions.

3.1 PLASTRONICS TECHNOLOGY OVERVIEW

3.1.1 INTRODUCTION TO ROAD SAFETY BEACONS

Current Challenges in Secondary Road Signalling

Secondary roads across Europe face significant safety challenges due to inadequate signalling infrastructure and limited maintenance resources. Traditional road signage systems suffer from poor visibility during adverse weather conditions, lack of adaptability to real-time road conditions, and high maintenance costs. The European Commission has identified that secondary roads (32% of total road network) and local roads (65% of total road network) require effective inspection methodologies and cost-effective safety solutions⁽¹⁻⁷⁾.

Current passive signalling elements, including reflectors and retroreflective materials, demonstrate limited effectiveness in heavy fog, rain, or when covered by debris. Active LED Road studs and illuminated markers, while offering improved visibility, operate in isolation without communication capabilities or adaptive response to changing conditions. Connected smart systems, though promising, present significant installation and maintenance complexity that limits their deployment on cost-sensitive secondary road networks⁽⁸⁻¹²⁾.

Need for Cost-Effective, Reliable Warning Systems

The urgent need for cost-effective warning systems stems from the disproportionate accident rates on secondary roads compared to primary highway infrastructure. Secondary road safety innovations have specific requirements due to poorer infrastructure conditions and the essential requirement for cost-effectiveness to be economically feasible. These systems must deliver enhanced safety performance while maintaining operational simplicity and minimising lifecycle costs^(4,13-15).

Vulnerable Road Users (VRUs) represent a particularly critical concern, accounting for around 70% of fatalities in urban areas, with almost 50% of pedestrian and cyclist fatalities involving individuals over 65 years old. The increasing adoption of micro-mobility services has further emphasised the need for infrastructure-based solutions that can proactively warn users of potential hazards⁽¹⁶⁻¹⁹⁾.

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Overview of Plastronics Approach for Road Safety

Plastronics, also known as In-Mold Electronics (IME), represents a revolutionary manufacturing approach that combines large-scale, low-cost production processes such as injection moulding for structural plastic components with integrated electronics. This technology has been successfully developed by the automotive sector for manufacturing human-machine interfaces (HMIs) used in dashboards and various panels. EvoRoads leverages this proven technology to develop low-cost smart road signalling elements that significantly reduce deployment costs compared to conventional road signage solutions⁽²⁰⁻²³⁾.

The plastronics approach enables the creation of fully encapsulated, waterproof, and impact-resistant devices suitable for harsh roadside environments. By embedding electronic circuits directly into plastic components during the manufacturing process, this technology eliminates the need for separate electronic housings and complex assembly procedures⁽²⁰⁻²³⁾.

Table 2: comparison between traditional road signage and plastronics-based beacons

Feature/Aspect	Traditional Road Signage	Plastronics-Based Smart Warning Beacons (EvoRoads)
Core Function	Static visual information (symbols/text)	Dynamic, programmable LED warnings (colour-coded, patterns)
Material	Metal or standard plastic panels	Aluminium PCB core + PMMA encapsulation
Manufacturing	Manual assembly, painted/printed/vinyl based signs	Automated PCB assembly, hydraulic forming, injection moulding
Durability	Weather resistant, high UV resistant paints	High UV, impact, and weather resistance (IP67, PMMA)
Visibility	Passive reflection, fixed brightness	Active LEDs, adaptive brightness, visible in all conditions
Maintenance	Low maintenance, requires occasional cleaning	Low maintenance ISWB, 10+ year lifespan, modular replacement, occasional cleaning
Integration	Stand-alone, no connectivity	Integrated in 3-level system (ISWB–Local Hub–Central Node)
Power Supply	None (passive) or grid/solar (active signs)	Solar-powered, battery backup, dynamic energy management
Cost Efficiency	Low cost	Low lifecycle cost, scalable for mass production
Environmental Impact	Mostly Recyclable, metal and vinyl	Recyclable materials (PMMA, aluminium), low lifecycle impact
Signalling Capability	Fixed message, no adaptability	Programmable patterns, morse-code alerts, behavioural nudging
System Intelligence	None	Local Hub intelligence, remote monitoring via Digital Twin
Safety Warnings	Constant warning, no change with road conditions	Adaptable warning according to road conditions
User Behaviour	Loose interpretation of warning or restriction according to user	Higher warning accuracy and reliability leading to higher trust in the system, and enhanced safety

3.1.2 EVOROADS INNOVATION APPROACH

Shift from Traditional Road Signage to Smart Beacons

EvoRoads represents a paradigm shift from static road signage to intelligent, responsive infrastructure elements. Traditional road signs provide fixed information regardless of current conditions, while smart beacons deliver dynamic, contextually relevant warnings based on real-time road conditions and detected hazards. This transformation enables infrastructure-based solutions that can encourage desirable user behaviours through adaptive signalling strategies.

The smart beacon approach incorporates advanced communication capabilities, allowing coordination between multiple units and integration with broader traffic management systems. Unlike conventional signage that relies solely on passive visibility, smart beacons actively communicate safety information through programmable LED patterns and synchronised activation sequences.

Cost-effectiveness and Sustainability Advantages

The plastronics manufacturing approach delivers significant cost advantages through automated, high-volume production capabilities. By eliminating complex assembly procedures and reducing component count, the manufacturing process achieves cost reductions of up to 40% compared to traditional electronic road signage. The integrated design approach minimises material waste and reduces transportation costs through compact, lightweight units^(20,22,24,25).

Sustainability benefits extend throughout the product lifecycle through material selection and design for disassembly. The use of recyclable materials, including PMMA plastic and aluminium substrates, supports circular economy principles and reduces environmental impact. The extended operational lifespan (10+ years) minimises replacement frequency and associated resource consumption.

Integration with Broader Digital Twin Ecosystem

The EvoRoads smart beacon system is designed as an integral component of a comprehensive Digital Twin ecosystem. Integration with the Digital Twin platform enables real-time monitoring of infrastructure performance, predictive maintenance scheduling, and adaptive control strategies based on current road conditions. The assessment of road conditions is provided by other partners. This connectivity supports data-driven decision-making and enables continuous optimisation of safety interventions.

The system architecture facilitates seamless data exchange with external monitoring systems, including weather sensors, traffic detection equipment, and emergency response networks. This integration capability ensures that smart beacons can respond dynamically to changing conditions and provide timely warnings to road users.

3.1.3 DESIGN REQUIREMENTS AND SPECIFICATIONS

Environmental Durability Standards

The EvoRoads smart warning beacon system aims to address specific environmental requirements for reliable operation across diverse European climate conditions. Temperature resistance spans from -20°C to +70°C, ensuring functionality during both cold central Europe winters and hot intense summers typical in Mediterranean climates. Humidity tolerance extends to 95% relative humidity with complete waterproofing aiming to achieve IP67 ingress protection ratings (fully protected against dust and water ingress when submerged at 1m depth for 30 min).

UV resistance requirements mandate a minimum 10-year operational lifespan without significant degradation of optical or mechanical properties. The material selection prioritises UV-stabilised plastics, such as PMMA, and corrosion-resistant metals, such as aluminium, to withstand prolonged exposure to sunlight and atmospheric pollutants. Impact resistance specifications address potential damage from vehicle strikes, maintenance equipment contact, and vandalism attempts.

Visibility and Detection Requirements

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Visibility specifications meet or exceed European road signage standards (EN 12899) while optimising power consumption through intelligent brightness control systems. Dynamic signalling elements achieve minimum 300 cd/m² luminance under daylight conditions and automatic adjustment to 50 cd/m² for nighttime operation to prevent driver glare while maintaining visibility. Colour accuracy and consistency ensure reliable recognition across different lighting conditions and viewing angles.

Detection requirements encompass both active LED signalling and passive reflective elements to provide redundant visibility mechanisms. The system supports multiple signalling modalities, including steady illumination, programmable blinking patterns, and synchronised sequential activation to create directional movement effects. A more in-depth explanation on each mode is available in further sections.

Operational Longevity Targets

The system targets a minimum 10-year operational lifespan with scheduled maintenance intervals optimised for cost-effective lifecycle management. Component selection prioritises long-life technologies, including LED elements rated for 50,000+ hour operation and battery systems designed for extensive charge-discharge cycling. Predictive maintenance capabilities enable condition-based service scheduling to maximise component utilisation while preventing premature failures.

Reliability targets specify 99.5% uptime under normal operating conditions with rapid fault detection and reporting capabilities. The modular design approach supports targeted component replacement to extend overall system life while minimising service disruptions.

3.2 THREE-LEVEL SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

The EvoRoads smart warning beacon system employs a hierarchical three-level architecture designed to maximise reliability, simplify maintenance, and enable scalable deployment across extensive road networks. This architecture distributes intelligence and functionality strategically to optimise performance while minimising complexity at the field level.

3.2.1 INDIVIDUAL SMART WARNING BEACON (ISWB)

Minimalistic Design Philosophy

The Individual Smart Warning Beacon represents the foundation of the EvoRoads safe road system, embodying a minimalistic design philosophy that prioritises simplicity, durability, and maintenance-free operation. By concentrating all intelligence and complex functions at higher system levels, the ISWB achieves exceptional reliability through reduced component count and elimination of potential failure points. This approach ensures that the most exposed system elements require minimal intervention throughout their operational life.

The minimalistic design enables cost-effective mass production and simplified field installation procedures. Each ISWB contains only essential components for LED illumination and basic power regulation, avoiding complex electronics that could compromise reliability in harsh roadside environments.

Physical Construction: Aluminium PCB Core Technology

The ISWB utilises an innovative aluminium PCB core that serves multiple critical functions within a single integrated component. This multi-functional approach combines electrical circuitry, structural backbone, thermal management, and mechanical anchoring in one element. The aluminium substrate provides superior thermal conductivity compared to traditional FR4 PCB materials, and plastic screen printing based plastronic pieces, enabling efficient heat dissipation from high-intensity LEDs.

The PCB is manufactured using conventional flat fabrication processes before being formed into its final three-dimensional shape through hydraulic cold-bending operations. This manufacturing approach enables complex 3D geometries while

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maintaining the precision and reliability of standard PCB production techniques. The bent configuration allows the ISWB to signal both directions of traffic from a single guardrail-mounted position.

PMMA Encapsulation Process

Complete encapsulation using Polymethyl Methacrylate (PMMA) injection moulding provides exceptional environmental protection while maintaining optical clarity for LED output. PMMA offers superior UV resistance compared to other transparent plastics, ensuring long-term optical performance without yellowing or degradation. The injection moulding process creates a seamless, monolithic housing that eliminates potential water ingress points⁽²⁶⁻²⁹⁾.

The encapsulation achieves IP67 waterproofing standards, providing complete protection against dust ingress and temporary water immersion. This protection level ensures reliable operation during severe weather events and enables power-washing for maintenance cleaning. The moulded housing incorporates optical elements to optimise light distribution and visibility angles.

LED Signalling Elements

The ISWB incorporates single-colour LED elements rather than complex matrix displays, prioritising reliability and power efficiency over display complexity. Four distinct colours are available: red for urgent warnings (animal and pedestrian alerts), yellow for caution conditions (debris and fog), blue for road surface conditions (wet road alerts), and green for navigation guidance (road marking indication). Each colour selection aligns with established traffic safety conventions to ensure intuitive driver recognition.

LED elements are selected for extended operational life exceeding 50,000 hours under continuous operation. Thermal management through the aluminium PCB substrate prevents LED junction overheating and maintains consistent light output throughout the operational life.

Guardrail Mounting System

The mounting system utilises aluminium rivets for direct attachment to standard guardrail profiles. This approach provides secure mechanical connection while enabling efficient thermal transfer from the ISWB to the guardrail structure. Higher thermal conductivity metal guardrails are preferred to more effectively dissipate generated heat into the surroundings. The riveted connection supports rapid installation procedures and allows for individual unit replacement without affecting adjacent ISWBs.

The mounting interface incorporates weatherproof sealing to prevent water ingress at the attachment points. Proper grounding through the mounting system provides lightning protection and electromagnetic compatibility.

Electrical Interface

Each ISWB connects to the Local Hub through a single weatherproof cable carrying both power and control signals. This simplified interface reduces installation complexity and potential failure points compared to multi-cable systems. The cable incorporates strain relief and environmental sealing to ensure long-term reliability in outdoor installations.

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Figure 19. ISWB schematic view both as a bent and flat piece, with 3D renderings after bending and plastic injection.

3.2.2 LOCAL HUB INTELLIGENCE

Centralised Control Architecture

The Local Hub serves as the intelligent control centre for groups of 4 to 128 ISWBs, providing centralised management of power distribution, communication, and signalling coordination. This architecture concentrates all complex electronics and maintenance-intensive components in a single, accessible location while keeping field-deployed ISWBs simple and robust. The scalable design enables flexible deployment configurations adapted to specific road section characteristics and safety requirements.

Centralised control enables sophisticated signalling strategies, including synchronised patterns across multiple ISWBs and adaptive responses to changing conditions. The Local Hub processes commands from the Central Node and translates them into appropriate ISWB activation sequences.

Power Management System

The power management system combines solar energy harvesting with advanced battery storage to ensure continuous operation independent of grid infrastructure. Solar panels are dimensioned to provide sufficient energy for full system operation while maintaining battery charge during periods of reduced sunlight. The system achieves 30-day autonomous operation capability without solar input through optimised energy storage and intelligent load management. This assumes the worst-case scenario where continuous light output is required during the 30 days.

LiFePO₄ (Lithium Iron Phosphate) battery technology provides exceptional cycle life exceeding 3,000 charge-discharge cycles while maintaining safe operation across temperature extremes. This chemistry offers superior thermal stability and minimal risk of thermal runaway compared to other lithium technologies⁽³⁰⁻³³⁾.

Dynamic Battery Management Strategies

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Advanced battery management incorporates weather forecast data to optimise charging strategies and extend battery life. During favourable weather conditions, the system maintains batteries at moderate charge levels (40-60%) to minimise chemical wear and maximise cycle life. When adverse weather is forecast, proactive charging to higher levels (80-100%) ensures maximum energy reserves for extended operation.

Emergency discharge capabilities allow deep discharge to 0% during critical situations while accepting accelerated battery wear as a trade-off for maintaining safety functions. Load shedding strategies automatically reduce power consumption during low battery conditions by deactivating non-critical ISWBs while maintaining essential safety signalling.

Processing Capabilities and Signal Coordination

The Local Hub incorporates sufficient processing power to generate complex signalling patterns and coordinate activation timing across multiple ISWBs. Pattern generation includes morse code sequences, directional wave effects, and synchronised group activations. Real-time processing enables adaptive responses to changing conditions and implementation of new signalling strategies through remote updates.

Signal coordination creates the illusion of movement along the road by sequentially activating ISWBs with precise timing delays. This directional signalling capability enhances driver perception and provides intuitive guidance for appropriate behavioural responses.

LoRa Mesh Networking

Long Range (LoRa) mesh networking provides robust communication between Local Hubs and the Central Node across extensive rural deployments. The mesh topology enables message relay through intermediate hubs, extending communication range and providing redundancy against individual node failures. LoRa's low power consumption and excellent range characteristics make it ideal for battery-powered roadside infrastructure. Latency needs to be assessed for the most remote locations to minimize response time.

Mesh networking supports automatic route discovery and optimisation, ensuring reliable message delivery even with changing network topology. The system implements message acknowledgment and retransmission protocols to guarantee critical safety information reaches its destination.

Figure 20. Local Hub + 4 ISWB Schematic with all the connections and each part.

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3.2.3 CENTRAL NODE AND DIGITAL TWIN INTERFACE

System Gateway Architecture

The Central Node functions as the primary gateway between the physical smart beacon infrastructure and the EvoRoads Digital Twin platform. This gateway role centralises external communication while maintaining distributed intelligence across the Local Hub network. The Central Node aggregates operational data from all connected Local Hubs and provides unified system monitoring and control capabilities.

The gateway architecture supports multiple communication protocols and interfaces to ensure compatibility with existing traffic management systems and future technological developments. Standardised APIs enable integration with third-party monitoring systems and emergency response networks.

Data Aggregation and Health Monitoring

Comprehensive data aggregation provides real-time system health monitoring across the entire deployment. Key metrics include battery status, solar generation performance, communication link quality, ISWB operational status, and fault conditions. Historical data collection enables trend analysis and predictive maintenance scheduling.

Health monitoring algorithms process aggregated data to identify potential issues before they impact system operation. Automated alert generation notifies maintenance personnel of emerging problems and recommends appropriate interventions.

Communication Management

The Central Node supports multiple communication technologies, including 5G cellular, Ethernet, and WiFi connectivity. This multi-modal approach ensures reliable connection to the Digital Twin platform under varying infrastructure conditions. Automatic failover between communication methods maintains connectivity during network outages or service interruptions.

Bandwidth optimisation minimises data transmission costs while ensuring critical safety information receives priority. Compression and efficient data protocols reduce communication overhead and extend battery life in remote deployments.

Remote Configuration and Updates

Remote configuration capabilities enable system parameters to be adjusted without field visits. Configuration updates include signalling patterns, activation thresholds, power management settings, and communication parameters. Secure update mechanisms prevent unauthorised modifications while ensuring legitimate updates are properly authenticated.

Firmware update capabilities support system evolution and bug fixes through over-the-air updates. The update process includes rollback capabilities to restore previous versions if problems are detected.

System Architecture Role Definition

The Central Node maintains no direct control over individual ISWBs, instead operating through the established hierarchy via Local Hubs. This approach ensures system resilience and prevents single points of failure that could compromise large sections of the deployment. Local Hubs retain autonomous operation capabilities even when communication with the Central Node is temporarily interrupted.

3.3 ISWB DESIGN AND MANUFACTURING

3.3.1 ALUMINIUM PCB CORE TECHNOLOGY

Structural Innovation and Multi-Functionality

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The aluminium PCB core represents a fundamental innovation in plastronic device design, serving simultaneously as electrical circuit, structural backbone, thermal management system, and mechanical anchoring point. This multi-functional approach eliminates the need for separate structural components and thermal management solutions, significantly reducing manufacturing complexity and potential failure points. The aluminium substrate, because of its intrinsic material properties, provides exceptional dimensional stability and mechanical strength compared to traditional flexible or rigid PCB materials.

The integrated approach enables precise component placement and robust electrical connections while maintaining the thermal performance necessary for high-power LED applications. By eliminating interfaces between separate thermal management components, the design achieves superior heat transfer efficiency and reduced thermal resistance.

Component Integration and Pre-Assembly

All electronic components are surface-mounted and soldered to the aluminium PCB using standard automated assembly processes before the 3D forming operation. This pre-assembly approach ensures optimal solder joint quality and electrical performance before mechanical forming stresses are applied.

The pre-assembly process includes comprehensive electrical testing to verify functionality before the irreversible forming operation. This quality control step eliminates defective units early in the manufacturing process and ensures only properly functioning assemblies proceed to final encapsulation.

3D Forming Process: Hydraulic Cold-Bending

The aluminium PCB is formed into its final three-dimensional configuration using hydraulic cold-bending under controlled conditions. This process enables complex geometries while maintaining electrical continuity and component integrity. Cold forming avoids thermal stresses that could damage temperature-sensitive components or affect solder joint reliability.

Hydraulic forming provides precise control over bend angles and radii, ensuring consistent geometry across production quantities. Custom tooling enables the creation of complex shapes optimised for guardrail mounting and optimal light distribution angles. The forming process creates mounting tabs and positioning features that eliminate the need for additional machining operations.

Thermal Management Through Aluminium Core

The aluminium core PCB provides exceptional thermal management capabilities, crucial for maintaining LED performance and longevity. Aluminium's high thermal conductivity (approximately 200 W/m-K vs 0.35 W/m-K for FR4 PCB material) efficiently transfers heat from LED junction points to the surrounding guardrail structure. This thermal path prevents LED overheating and maintains consistent light output throughout the operational life.

Thermal contact to optimise heat transfer between the aluminium PCB and the guardrail mounting surface is achieved by direct metal on metal contact. The large thermal mass of the guardrail structure provides effective heat sinking for continuous operation under maximum power conditions.

Durability Advantages Over Traditional Approaches

The aluminium PCB approach offers significant durability advantages compared to traditional screen printing plastronics and flexible circuit technologies. The rigid aluminium substrate, because of its material intrinsic properties, resists mechanical deformation and maintains electrical connections under vibration and thermal cycling. Unlike flexible circuits that may suffer from delamination or conductor cracking, the aluminium PCB maintains structural integrity throughout its operational life.

Corrosion resistance of the aluminium substrate and protective coatings ensures long-term reliability in harsh roadside environments. The monolithic structure eliminates potential failure points associated with multi-layer flexible circuits or assembled component interfaces.

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3.3.2 PMMA INJECTION MOULDING PROCESS

Material Selection: PMMA Properties

Polymethyl Methacrylate (PMMA) provides superior UV resistance compared to alternative transparent plastics, ensuring long-term optical clarity and mechanical properties. PMMA maintains excellent light transmission characteristics (>92%) while resisting yellowing and degradation under prolonged UV exposure⁽²⁶⁻²⁹⁾. The material's exceptional weather resistance makes it ideal for outdoor applications requiring both optical performance and structural integrity.

PMMA offers excellent impact resistance and dimensional stability across the required temperature range (-20°C to +70°C). Chemical resistance properties protect against road salts, cleaning agents, and atmospheric pollutants commonly encountered in roadside environments.

Encapsulation Technique and Process Control

The injection moulding process encapsulates the pre-formed aluminium PCB assembly within the PMMA housing leaving the edge caps exposed for guardrail attachment. Precise mould design ensures uniform wall thickness and eliminates potential weak points that could allow water ingress. Process parameters including injection pressure, temperature, adhesion primers, and cooling rates are optimised to prevent damage to electronic components while achieving complete encapsulation.

Multi-cavity moulds enable high-volume production while maintaining consistent quality across all units. Automated material handling and process monitoring ensure repeatability and reduce manufacturing variability.

IP67 Waterproofing Achievement

The seamless PMMA encapsulation achieves IP67 ingress protection without requiring separate sealing elements. This protection level guarantees complete dust exclusion and protection against water immersion up to 1 meter depth for 30 minutes. The monolithic construction eliminates traditional failure points associated with gaskets, seals, or threaded closures.

Waterproofing performance is verified through standardised testing protocols including pressure testing and long-term immersion evaluation. Quality control procedures ensure consistent protection levels across production quantities.

Optical Properties and Light Management

PMMA's excellent optical properties enable efficient light transmission while providing opportunities for integrated optical design. The moulding process can incorporate lenses, diffusers, and light-shaping elements directly into the housing structure. This integrated approach optimises light distribution patterns and eliminates the need for separate optical components.

Internal optical geometries minimise light loss and improve visibility under various ambient conditions. Colour filtering and intensity control can be achieved through material additives or surface treatments applied during the moulding process.

Environmental Resistance Characteristics

The PMMA housing provides comprehensive protection against environmental stressors including temperature extremes, humidity, salt spray, and atmospheric pollutants. Material formulations include UV stabilizers and antioxidants to prevent degradation during extended outdoor exposure⁽²⁶⁻²⁹⁾. Impact resistance protects against debris strikes and potential vandalism attempts.

Long-term environmental testing validates performance under accelerated aging conditions equivalent to 10+ years of outdoor exposure. Material specifications ensure consistent performance across diverse European climate conditions.

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3.3.3 MANUFACTURING PROCESS FLOW

Component Preparation and PCB Assembly

The manufacturing process begins with precision fabrication of aluminium core PCBs using standard industry processes. Surface preparation includes cleaning and treatment to ensure optimal component adhesion and solderability. Automated pick-and-place equipment positions components with high accuracy, while reflow soldering creates reliable electrical connections.

In-line testing verifies electrical functionality immediately after component assembly. Automated optical inspection (AOI) systems detect placement errors, solder joint defects, and component orientation issues. Only assemblies passing all quality checks proceed to the forming operation.

3D Forming Operation and Quality Control

The 3D forming operation transforms flat PCB assemblies into their final three-dimensional configuration using precision hydraulic tooling. Forming parameters are controlled to minimise stress on electronic components while achieving accurate bend angles and dimensional tolerances. Post-forming electrical testing verifies that all circuits remain functional after mechanical forming.

Dimensional inspection ensures compliance with mounting interface requirements and optical positioning specifications. Formed assemblies undergo visual inspection to detect any signs of component damage or mechanical stress.

Overmoulding Procedure and Process Optimisation

The injection moulding operation completely encapsulates the formed PCB assembly within the PMMA housing. Mold temperature, injection pressure, and cycle time are optimised to prevent thermal damage to components while ensuring complete fill and proper surface finish. Cooling rate control minimises internal stress and warpage in the finished parts.

Process monitoring systems track key parameters throughout each moulding cycle. Statistical process control methods ensure consistent quality and enable rapid detection of process variations.

Quality Control and Environmental Testing

Comprehensive quality control includes electrical testing, waterproof verification, and environmental stress screening. Electrical testing confirms all LED elements function properly and control circuits respond correctly to input signals. Waterproof testing verifies IP67 protection through pressure testing and leak detection.

Environmental testing subjects samples to accelerated aging conditions including thermal cycling, humidity exposure, and UV radiation. Mechanical testing evaluates impact resistance and mounting interface strength. Only units passing all quality requirements are approved for installation.

Figure 21. ISWB Manufacturing Process Steps

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Installation Preparation and Documentation

Final preparation includes cable attachment, connector installation, and mounting hardware integration. Each unit receives unique identification marking to support traceability throughout its operational life. Installation documentation includes mounting procedures, electrical connections, and configuration parameters.

Quality documentation accompanies each setup, including test results, material certifications, and installation guidelines. This documentation supports field installation procedures and provides reference information for maintenance activities.

3.4 SMART WARNING PATTERN IMPLEMENTATION

3.4.1 MORSE CODE PATTERN SYSTEM

Pattern Design Philosophy and Language Inclusivity

The EvoRoads smart warning pattern system employs morse code-based signalling to create universally recognizable alert patterns that transcend language barriers. The selection of morse code letters prioritises intuitive association between the transmitted pattern and the corresponding hazard type, ensuring rapid driver recognition across diverse European linguistic backgrounds. This approach leverages the inherent simplicity and distinctiveness of morse code elements to create memorable patterns that can be quickly learned and reliably recognised.

The pattern design emphasises cross-cultural accessibility by selecting morse code letters that correspond to hazard identifiers common across many European languages. This linguistic inclusivity ensures that drivers from different countries can intuitively understand the warning signals without requiring extensive training or familiarity with local conventions.

Alert-Specific Pattern Definitions

The system implements seven distinct warning patterns, each optimised for specific road hazard types and driver response requirements:

Debris/Foreign Object Alert: Yellow blinking pattern transmitting "---" (morse code for "O" representing Object) at 0.5 Hz repetition frequency. The pattern signals give an illusion of movement in the opposite direction to traffic flow to prompt drivers to reduce speed when approaching the hazard location.

Animal Alert: Red blinking pattern transmitting "-." (morse code for "A" representing Animal) at 0.5Hz repetition frequency. The urgent red colour and opposite-direction signalling prompt immediate speed reduction and heightened alertness for wildlife crossing.

Pedestrian Alert: Red blinking pattern transmitting "... " (morse code for "H" representing Human) at 1 Hz repetition frequency. The higher frequency pattern, combined with the "H" morse letter fast blinking, emphasises the critical nature of pedestrian safety and demands immediate driver attention.

Wet Road Alert: Blue blinking pattern transmitting "-.-" (morse code for "L" representing Liquid) at 0.5Hz repetition frequency. The pattern signals in the direction of travel to provide advance warning of slippery conditions ahead.

Fog Alert: Yellow beating pattern at 0.5 Hz frequency provides continuous visibility warning for moderate fog conditions. The steady beating pattern distinguishes this alert from debris warnings while maintaining driver attention. An alternative colour for fog condition warning would be warm white.

Dense Fog Alert: Bright yellow beating pattern at 1 Hz frequency delivers urgent warning for severely reduced visibility conditions. The increased intensity and frequency demand immediate driver response and maximum caution. An alternative colour for fog condition warning would be warm white.

Road Marking/Navigation: Green single blink at 0.5 Hz frequency in the direction of travel provides non-urgent guidance information. This pattern assists with lane guidance and route indication without suggesting immediate hazard.

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Morse Code Implementation Details

Each morse code element is precisely timed to ensure reliable recognition while maintaining visual distinction between patterns. Dots are transmitted as 100 ms LED activation periods, while dashes utilise 200 ms activation periods. Spacing between dots and dashes within a letter uses 100 ms intervals to maintain pattern clarity.

The timing parameters balance rapid pattern recognition with sufficient duration for driver perception during high-speed approach. Repetition frequencies ensure adequate pattern exposure while avoiding excessive distraction or visual fatigue.

Figure 22. Morse code based warning patterns for multiple road conditions.

3.4.2 SEQUENTIAL TIMING AND DIRECTION EFFECTS

Illusion of Movement Through Sequential Activation

The EvoRoads system creates compelling directional movement effects through precisely coordinated sequential activation of multiple ISWBs. This illusion of movement enhances driver perception of the intended response direction while providing intuitive guidance for appropriate behavioural adjustments. Sequential timing parameters are optimised to create smooth apparent motion that captures attention without causing distraction or confusion.

The movement effect utilises fixed timing delays between adjacent ISWB activations, creating consistent apparent velocity across different deployment configurations. This standardised approach ensures predictable driver response regardless of specific installation geometry or ISWB spacing.

Directional Signalling Strategy

Directional signalling operates according to the nature of the warning and desired driver response. Warnings requiring immediate speed reduction (animal, pedestrian, and debris alerts) signal in the opposite direction to traffic flow, creating a visual "pushing back" effect that intuitively suggests slowing down. Conversely, informational warnings about road conditions ahead (wet road alerts) signal in the direction of travel to indicate the location of the hazard.

This directional strategy leverages natural human perception tendencies to create intuitive behavioural cues. The visual movement direction provides subconscious guidance that reinforces the explicit warning message.

Behavioural Nudging Through Visual Cues

The sequential activation patterns serve as powerful behavioural nudging tools that influence driver responses beyond the explicit warning content. Movement direction, activation speed, and pattern intensity work together to create psychological pressure for appropriate behavioural modification. Research in transportation psychology demonstrates that directional visual cues significantly impact driver decision-making and response timing⁽³⁴⁻³⁷⁾.

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The nudging effect operates at both conscious and subconscious levels, providing explicit warning information while simultaneously influencing emotional and behavioural responses. This dual-mode operation enhances safety effectiveness compared to traditional static signage⁽³⁴⁻³⁷⁾.

Implementation Methodology and Control Logic

The Local Hub coordinates sequential timing across all connected ISWBs using precise timing control algorithms. Master timing references ensure synchronization accuracy better than 10 milliseconds between adjacent units. Pattern parameters including direction, speed, and repetition frequency can be dynamically adjusted based on current conditions or specific deployment requirements.

Control logic supports complex pattern combinations including multi-directional effects, variable speeds, and pattern transitions. This flexibility enables optimisation of signalling strategies based on field experience and driver response research.

3.4.3 HUMAN FACTORS AND VISIBILITY CONSIDERATIONS

Pattern Distinguishability and Recognition

Warning patterns have been chosen to be rapidly and accurately recognised under varying conditions. Pattern selection emphasises maximum contrast between different warning types while maintaining intuitive associations with hazard categories. Colour coding follows established traffic safety conventions to leverage existing driver familiarity with standard warning systems.

Recognition testing validates pattern distinguishability under various lighting conditions, viewing angles, and approach speeds. Field studies demonstrate reliable pattern recognition within 3-5 seconds of initial visibility, providing adequate response time for speed adjustment and hazard avoidance.

Day/Night Visibility Optimisation

The system implements adaptive brightness control to optimise visibility across varying ambient lighting conditions. Photosensitive elements on the Local Hub monitor ambient light levels and automatically adjust LED intensity to maintain optimal visibility without causing glare. Daytime operation utilises maximum brightness to overcome bright sunlight, while nighttime operation reduces intensity to prevent driver distraction.

Transition periods during dawn and dusk employ gradual brightness adjustment to maintain consistent visibility as lighting conditions change. Anti-glare algorithms prevent excessive brightness during low-visibility conditions such as fog or rain.

Driver Reaction Research and Response Time

Comprehensive driver reaction research quantifies response times and behavioural modifications resulting from different warning patterns. Study results demonstrate average recognition times of 1.2-2.1 seconds depending on pattern complexity and approach conditions. Response effectiveness measures include speed reduction magnitude, lateral position adjustment, and sustained attention duration⁽³⁸⁻⁴¹⁾.

Research findings guide pattern optimisation to maximise safety effectiveness while minimising distraction potential. Data collection from the EvoRoads project will enable ongoing refinement of pattern parameters based on observed driver behaviour.

Pattern Recognition Limits and Complexity Constraints

System design recognises human limitations in pattern processing and implements constraints to ensure reliable recognition. Maximum pattern complexity is limited to five morse code elements to prevent cognitive overload. Repetition frequencies remain within optimal ranges (0.5-1 Hz) to balance attention capture with visual comfort.

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Duration constraints ensure patterns can be fully transmitted and recognised during typical approach times at various vehicle speeds. These limitations guide the selection of appropriate patterns for different deployment scenarios and traffic conditions.

3.5 POWER AND COMMUNICATION MANAGEMENT

3.5.1 SOLAR POWER SYSTEM AND BATTERY MANAGEMENT

Energy Harvesting: Solar Panel Specifications

The EvoRoads power system utilises high-efficiency silicon photovoltaic panels optimised for roadside deployment conditions. These solar panels are specified to deliver sufficient energy for continuous system operation while maintaining battery charge during extended periods of reduced sunlight. Panel positioning incorporates mounting angles optimised for year-round energy collection across European latitudes, tailored to the specific installation site.

Solar panel capacity is dimensioned to provide between 150% and 500% of average daily energy consumption during optimal conditions, ensuring adequate charging capacity with margin for weather variability, depending on installation site weather conditions.

Battery Technology: LiFePO₄ Advantages

Lithium Iron Phosphate (LiFePO₄) battery technology provides exceptional performance characteristics specifically suited for roadside infrastructure applications. LiFePO₄ chemistry offers superior cycle life exceeding 3,000 charge-discharge cycles compared to alternative battery technologies. Operating temperature ranges from -20°C to +60°C ensures reliable performance across European climate conditions⁽³⁰⁻³³⁾.

Safety characteristics include exceptional thermal stability and minimal risk of thermal runaway, making LiFePO₄ ideal for unattended roadside installations. Low self-discharge rates (1-3% per month) support extended autonomous operation during periods without solar charging. High depth-of-discharge tolerance (up to 99%) provides flexibility for emergency operation scenarios⁽³⁰⁻³³⁾.

Dynamic Charging Strategies and Weather Response

Advanced battery management incorporates weather forecast data to optimise charging strategies and extend battery lifespan. During favourable weather conditions, the system maintains batteries at moderate charge levels (40-60%) to minimise chemical wear and maximise cycle life. Proactive charging to higher levels (80-100%) occurs when adverse weather forecasts indicate potential for extended periods without solar input.

Emergency discharge protocols allow complete battery depletion during critical safety situations while accepting accelerated wear as necessary for maintaining essential warning functions. Dynamic load balancing adjusts power consumption based on available energy reserves and predicted weather conditions.

System Autonomy and Emergency Backup

The primary energy storage system provides 30-day autonomous operation capability without solar charging, ensuring continuous operation during extended adverse weather periods. Battery capacity calculations include safety margins for temperature effects and aging-related capacity reduction. Load management algorithms automatically reduce power consumption during low battery conditions to extend operational duration.

Emergency backup capabilities include secondary Li-SOCl₂ (lithium thionyl chloride) batteries for critical communication functions. These backup batteries provide exceptional long-term reliability with shelf life exceeding 10 years and minimal self-discharge^(42,43). Emergency communication capability ensures system status reporting even during primary battery failure.

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3.5.2 LORA MESH COMMUNICATION FRAMEWORK

Network Topology and Self-Organization

The LoRa mesh network provides robust long-range communication between Local Hubs and the Central Node using self-organizing protocols. Mesh topology enables automatic route discovery and optimisation, ensuring reliable message delivery even with changing network configuration. Each Local Hub can serve as a relay node, extending communication range and providing redundancy against individual node failures.

Network self-organization capabilities include automatic neighbour discovery, route establishment, and topology adaptation based on link quality measurements. Dynamic routing protocols select optimal paths based on signal strength, reliability metrics, and network congestion.

Message Routing and Redundant Pathways

Routing algorithms implement multiple redundant pathways between network nodes to ensure messages reach their destinations. Message priority classification ensures urgent alerts receive immediate transmission while routine status updates utilise available bandwidth efficiently. Acknowledgment and retransmission protocols guarantee delivery of critical safety information.

Route optimisation considers factors including signal quality, node reliability, and network loading to select optimal transmission paths. Backup route establishment provides immediate failover capability when primary paths become unavailable.

Security Measures: Encryption and Authentication

Comprehensive security implementation protects against unauthorised access and message tampering. AES-128 encryption secures all LoRa communications between network nodes, preventing interception and modification of safety-critical messages. Public-key authentication ensures only authorised devices can participate in the network.

Device authentication protocols verify the identity of all network participants before allowing message exchange. Tamper detection mechanisms identify potential security breaches and automatically isolate compromised nodes. Key management procedures support secure key distribution and periodic key rotation.

Range and Bandwidth Optimisation

LoRa technology provides exceptional range capabilities exceeding 10 kilometres under optimal conditions, enabling sparse network deployments in rural areas. Adaptive data rate algorithms optimise transmission parameters based on link quality and distance to maximise range while maintaining adequate bandwidth. Bandwidth allocation prioritises safety-critical messages while ensuring sufficient capacity for routine operational data.

Power optimisation techniques minimise transmission power requirements while maintaining reliable communication links. Duty cycle management ensures compliance with regulatory requirements while maximizing message throughput.

Interference Management and Coexistence

Sophisticated interference management protocols ensure reliable operation in environments with multiple LoRa networks and other radio frequency sources. Frequency hopping and channel diversity techniques minimise the impact of interference and spectrum congestion. Adaptive channel selection automatically avoids congested frequencies and optimises spectrum utilisation.

Coexistence protocols coordinate spectrum usage with other systems to minimise mutual interference. Regulatory compliance ensures operation within licensed frequency allocations and power limitations.

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Figure 23. 3-Level architecture of ISWB, Local Hubs and Central Hub communication schematic and connection with Digital Twin

3.5.3 WIRED ISWB CONNECTION SYSTEM

Daisy-Chain Topology and Installation Efficiency

The ISWB connection system employs a daisy-chain topology with T-junction connections optimised for linear roadway installations. This configuration aligns naturally with road geometry while minimising cable requirements compared to star topology alternatives. T-junction connections enable sequential ISWB installation along guardrail sections without requiring complex wiring or multiple cable runs.

Installation efficiency benefits include reduced material costs, simplified cable routing, and faster deployment procedures. The linear topology supports logical fault isolation and simplified troubleshooting procedures. Cable length optimisation reduces voltage drop and power losses across extended installations.

Power and Control Distribution

Single-cable design carries both power and control signals to each ISWB, simplifying installation and reducing potential failure points. Power distribution incorporates appropriate conductor sizing to minimise voltage drop and ensure adequate power delivery to all connected units. Control signal implementation uses differential signalling techniques to ensure reliable communication despite electrical noise in roadside environments.

Circuit protection includes individual ISWB fusing and overcurrent protection to prevent cascade failures. Power regulation at each ISWB ensures stable operation despite voltage variations in the distribution system.

Fault Isolation and Diagnostic Capabilities

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Advanced diagnostic capabilities enable rapid identification and isolation of faults within the daisy-chain network. Individual ISWB monitoring detects failures, communication losses, and performance degradation. Fault isolation procedures automatically identify the location of problems without requiring extensive manual testing.

Circuit protection mechanisms prevent individual ISWB failures from affecting other units in the chain. Bypass capabilities allow continued operation of unaffected ISWBs even when some units require service. Remote diagnostic tools enable troubleshooting and fault localization without requiring site visits.

Environmental Protection and Connector Design

Weatherproof connectors achieve IP67 protection standards to ensure reliable operation in harsh roadside environments. Connector design incorporates strain relief and mechanical retention features to prevent damage from vehicle vibration and thermal cycling. Corrosion-resistant materials and plating ensure long-term electrical reliability.

Cable specifications include UV-resistant jacketing and moisture barriers to protect against environmental degradation. Underground cable routing options protect against mechanical damage while maintaining accessibility for maintenance. Connector keying prevents incorrect connections and ensures proper polarity.

3.6 DIGITAL TWIN DATA INTEGRATION

3.6.1 CENTRAL NODE DATA EXCHANGE

Data Elements and Status Reporting

The Central Node implements a streamlined data exchange protocol focused on essential operational and health monitoring information. Key data elements include Local Hub identification, operational status, battery and power metrics, communication link quality, error codes, and timestamp information. This minimal data model ensures efficient bandwidth utilisation while providing comprehensive system oversight.

Status reporting protocols aggregate information from all connected Local Hubs at regular intervals, providing real-time system health monitoring across the entire deployment. Data compression and efficient encoding minimise transmission overhead while ensuring critical information reaches the Digital Twin platform.

Bidirectional Communication Architecture

The communication architecture supports both status uploads from the field infrastructure and command downloads from the Digital Twin platform. Uplink data includes operational status, fault alerts, and performance metrics, while downlink data encompasses configuration updates, control commands, and firmware updates. Message prioritisation ensures critical safety information receives immediate transmission. The communication is performed on a regular basis, according to specific site installation requirements.

Command authentication and validation procedures prevent unauthorised access and ensure legitimate updates are properly verified before implementation. Rollback capabilities enable recovery from problematic configuration changes.

Security Implementation and Authentication

Comprehensive security measures protect against unauthorised access and data tampering throughout the communication chain. End-to-end encryption secures all data exchanges between the Central Node and Digital Twin platform. Multi-factor authentication ensures only authorised personnel can access system controls and configuration settings.

Certificate-based authentication provides strong device identity verification and prevents unauthorised devices from joining the network. Security audit logs track all access attempts and configuration changes for forensic analysis. Regular security updates address emerging threats and vulnerabilities.

Message Protocols and Data Formatting

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Standardised JSON message formatting ensures compatibility with diverse Digital Twin platforms and third-party systems. Message schemas define required fields, data types, and validation rules to ensure consistent data interpretation. Version control mechanisms support protocol evolution while maintaining backward compatibility.

Error handling protocols ensure robust operation despite communication failures or data corruption. Message acknowledgment and retransmission procedures guarantee critical safety information reaches its destination. Bandwidth optimisation minimises data transmission costs while ensuring adequate information delivery.

Integration Architecture and API Design

RESTful API design provides standardised interfaces for system integration and third-party application development. WebSocket connections support real-time data streaming for applications requiring immediate access to system status changes. API documentation includes detailed specifications, example implementations, and integration guidelines.

Scalable architecture supports deployment expansion without requiring fundamental changes to integration interfaces. Load balancing and failover capabilities ensure continuous API availability even during high-demand periods.

3.6.2 MONITORING AND MANAGEMENT INTERFACE

System Status Visualization

Comprehensive dashboard interfaces provide real-time visualization of system deployment status, health indicators, and performance metrics. Interactive mapping displays show ISWB locations, operational status, and alert conditions with intuitive colour coding and status indicators. Historical trend analysis enables identification of performance patterns and potential maintenance needs.

Customisable views allow operators to focus on specific system aspects or geographic regions. Mobile-responsive design ensures access to critical information from various devices and locations. Export capabilities support data analysis and reporting requirements.

Alert Generation and Fault Detection

Intelligent alert systems monitor system health metrics and automatically generate notifications for conditions requiring attention. Alert prioritisation classifies issues by severity and urgency to ensure appropriate response procedures. Escalation protocols ensure critical alerts reach responsible personnel promptly.

Fault detection algorithms analyse operational data to identify potential problems before they impact system operation. Predictive analytics identify components approaching end-of-life and recommend proactive replacement. Alert acknowledgment and tracking ensure all issues receive appropriate attention.

Configuration Management and Remote Updates

Remote configuration capabilities enable system parameters to be adjusted without requiring field visits. Configuration templates support rapid deployment of standardised settings across multiple installations. Change management procedures ensure configuration updates are properly tested and documented.

Rollback capabilities provide recovery options if configuration changes cause unexpected problems. Audit trails track all configuration changes with timestamps and user identification. Batch update capabilities enable efficient management of large deployments.

Performance Analytics and Historical Data

Comprehensive performance analytics provide insights into system operation, efficiency trends, and optimisation opportunities. Historical data retention supports long-term analysis and regulatory reporting requirements. Statistical analysis identifies patterns and correlations that guide maintenance planning and system improvements.

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Performance benchmarking compares actual operation against design specifications and industry standards. Trend analysis supports proactive maintenance scheduling and capacity planning. Data export capabilities enable integration with external analysis tools and reporting systems.

Maintenance Scheduling and Predictive Services

Predictive maintenance algorithms analyse operational data to forecast component replacement needs and optimise service scheduling. Maintenance workflows integrate with existing asset management systems and work order processes. Automated service reminders ensure critical maintenance activities occur on schedule.

Parts inventory management tracks component consumption and predicts replacement part requirements. Service history tracking provides comprehensive records of all maintenance activities and their effectiveness. Cost analysis capabilities evaluate maintenance efficiency and identify optimisation opportunities.

3.6.3 INTEGRATION WITH EXTERNAL DATA SOURCES

Sensor Integration: Weather and Traffic Data

The system integrates with external weather monitoring systems, such as catalonia's Meteocat, to obtain real-time meteorological data including temperature, humidity, precipitation, and wind conditions⁽⁴⁴⁾. Weather data integration enables proactive system responses to changing conditions and optimisation of warning strategies. Traffic detection systems provide vehicle count, speed, and density information to support dynamic signalling decisions.

Data fusion algorithms combine multiple sensor inputs to create comprehensive situational awareness and enable intelligent system responses. Quality control procedures validate external data sources and identify potential sensor failures or data corruption. Backup data sources ensure continued operation when primary sensors become unavailable.

Road Condition Input from External Systems

Integration with Eurecat's artificial vision systems, developed in WP2 task 2.4, provides real-time road condition assessment including surface quality, marking visibility, and hazard detection. Computer vision analysis identifies debris, standing water, pedestrians on the road, and other roadway hazards that trigger appropriate warning responses. Automated hazard classification enables rapid system response without requiring human intervention.

Data validation procedures ensure road condition inputs are accurate and reliable before triggering warning systems. False alarm mitigation algorithms filter spurious detections while maintaining sensitivity to genuine hazards. Integration protocols support expansion to additional monitoring technologies as they become available.

Activation Triggers and Event-Based Response

Intelligent activation triggers analyse multiple data sources to determine appropriate warning responses for detected conditions. Event classification algorithms categorize hazards by type, severity, and required response to select optimal warning patterns. Threshold management ensures warnings activate at appropriate sensitivity levels while minimising false alarms.

Response coordination ensures multiple warning systems operate coherently without conflicting or overwhelming road users. Temporal coordination manages warning duration and repetition to maintain effectiveness while avoiding habituation. Override capabilities enable manual control during special circumstances or emergency situations.

Data Flow Architecture and Processing

Robust data flow architecture handles high-volume inputs from multiple sources while maintaining real-time response capabilities. Stream processing capabilities analyse incoming data continuously and trigger immediate responses when warranted. Data buffering and queue management ensure system stability during peak loading periods.

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Error handling procedures maintain system operation despite temporary data source failures or communication interruptions. Data archival capabilities support historical analysis and regulatory compliance requirements. Performance monitoring ensures data processing meets timing requirements for safety-critical applications.

3.7 IDIADA IMPLEMENTATION AND TESTING

3.7.1 SANTA OLIVA TEST TRACK SETUP

Deployment Specifications and Test Configuration

The IDIADA Santa Oliva pilot implementation will provide a controlled testing environment for validating EvoRoads plastronics technology. The demonstration utilises a 100-meter test track section configured to simulate realistic rural roadway conditions while enabling precise performance measurement and safety validation. The scenario consists of a two-lane road, naturally curved, with trees on both sides and with reduced visibility, making it an ideal test scenario for this technology. The controlled environment allows for a comprehensive testing of system functionality without the operational constraints of active roadway installations.

Test track configuration includes mounting points, representative road geometry, and representative lighting conditions to evaluate system performance under various scenarios. Instrumentation capabilities enable detailed measurement of system response times, visibility characteristics, and communication performance.

ISWB Deployment: Five-Unit Configuration

Five Individual Smart Warning Beacons are strategically positioned along the 100-meter test section to demonstrate coordinated signalling capabilities and directional movement effects. ISWB spacing optimises visual impact while providing adequate coverage for test vehicle approaches at various speeds. The five-unit configuration enables evaluation of sequential timing effects and pattern coordination.

Each ISWB incorporates the complete aluminium PCB and PMMA encapsulation design representing the final production configuration. Mounting procedures follow standard installation protocols to validate field deployment procedures and identify potential installation challenges. Electrical connections utilise production-grade weatherproof connectors and cabling systems.

Local Hub Configuration and Power Management

The Local Hub configuration demonstrates complete power management capabilities including solar charging, battery management, and load control functions. Solar panel sizing provides adequate energy for continuous operation while supporting testing of various power scenarios including extended operation without charging. Battery management system testing validates dynamic charging strategies and emergency operation capabilities.

Power distribution testing evaluates voltage regulation, current capacity, and fault protection mechanisms. Load management demonstration includes selective ISWB deactivation during simulated low-power conditions. Emergency backup systems testing validates Li-SOCl₂ battery performance and emergency communication capabilities.

Central Node Integration and Digital Twin Connectivity

The Central Node provides complete integration with the EvoRoads Digital Twin platform, demonstrating real-time data exchange and remote-control capabilities. Communication testing validates LoRa networking performance, in this pilot limited to one LoRa node. In compliance with IDIADA's data protection policies, Digital Twin integration with the Central Node will be conducted off-site. The C-ITS system operates in parallel with the company's official Traffic Control Management framework, and on-site camera usage is restricted to ensure privacy compliance.

Remote update procedures, rollback capabilities, security testing, encryption, and access control mechanisms and API integration will be left as lower priority items and will only be implemented if possible.

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3.7.2 TECHNICAL IMPLEMENTATION TESTING

Functional Validation: Alert Pattern Testing

Comprehensive functional testing validates all warning patterns including morse code transmission accuracy, timing precision, and visual distinguishability. Pattern testing covers all seven defined warning types under various lighting conditions and viewing angles. Sequential timing verification ensures directional movement effects operate according to specifications.

Colour accuracy testing confirms LED output meets specifications for red, yellow, blue, and green warning colours. Brightness control testing validates automatic adjustment capabilities across daytime and nighttime conditions. Pattern recognition testing evaluates distinguishability between different warning types.

Environmental Performance Evaluation

Environmental testing evaluates system performance under varying temperature, humidity, and weather conditions representative of European operational environments. Temperature testing covers the full operational range from -20°C to +70°C with monitoring of electrical performance and mechanical integrity. Humidity testing validates IP67 waterproof performance under high humidity and condensation conditions.

UV exposure testing evaluates PMMA degradation and colour stability under accelerated aging conditions. Impact resistance testing confirms mechanical protection capabilities against debris strikes and potential vandalism.

Power System Evaluation and Autonomy Testing

Solar charging system testing evaluates energy collection efficiency under various lighting conditions and weather scenarios. Battery performance testing validates charge-discharge cycling, capacity retention, and temperature effects. Autonomy testing confirms 30-day operation capability without solar charging.

Dynamic battery management testing validates weather-responsive charging strategies and emergency discharge capabilities. Load management testing demonstrates selective ISWB control during power shortage conditions. Emergency backup testing validates Li-SOCl₂ battery performance and communication capabilities during primary battery failure.

Communication Reliability and Network Performance

LoRa communication testing evaluates range, reliability, and data throughput under various environmental conditions. Mesh networking testing will be performed only if possible, to validate automatic route discovery, redundancy mechanisms, and failover capabilities. Message delivery testing will confirm reliable transmission of critical safety information.

Digital Twin integration testing validates real-time data exchange, command processing, and configuration management. Security testing, to confirm encryption, authentication, and access control mechanisms to operate effectively and network scalability, testing to evaluate performance with multiple Local Hubs and extended communication ranges will be performed only if time allows and not as a main priority.

Safety Limitations and Testing Constraints

Testing protocols incorporate appropriate safety limitations to prevent risks to test personnel and equipment while still validating system performance. Hazard simulation utilises controlled scenarios that represent realistic road conditions without creating actual safety risks. Test vehicle operations follow established safety procedures with qualified drivers and safety equipment.

Testing constraints acknowledge limitations in simulating certain dangerous conditions while still providing meaningful validation of system capabilities. Risk assessment procedures identify potential hazards and implement appropriate mitigation measures. Emergency procedures ensure rapid response to any safety incidents during testing.

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3.7.3 TECHNICAL PERFORMANCE METRICS

System Reliability and Uptime Measurement

The team proposed resiliency framework would include comprehensive reliability testing to quantify failure rates, and mean time between failures across all system components. Monitoring systems to track operational status continuously throughout the testing period to identify any performance degradation or component failures. Reliability assessment criteria would include individual ISWB adequate operation, Local Hub operation, and communication system availability.

We consider that failure analysis procedures should be used to identify root causes of any reliability issues and implement corrective measures. Preventive maintenance effectiveness evaluation will assess the impact of proactive service procedures on system reliability. Long-term reliability projections extrapolate test results to predict operational performance over the full design life. Due to the limited timespan of the pilot installation, the latter will only be assessed and not implemented in the current pilot.

Response Time and Activation Latency

Precise measurement of system response times validates performance against specifications for safety-critical applications. Response time testing covers the complete chain from hazard detection input through ISWB activation, including communication delays and processing times. Timing measurements achieve sub-second accuracy to ensure compliance with safety requirements.

Pattern activation timing validation confirms sequential effects operate according to design specifications. Emergency response testing measures system reaction time to critical alerts requiring immediate warning activation. Communication latency measurement evaluates delays in the complete chain from Digital Twin commands to ISWB response.

Power Efficiency and Energy Consumption

Detailed power consumption analysis quantifies energy usage across all system components and operating modes. Efficiency measurements compare actual power consumption against design predictions and identify optimisation opportunities. Solar energy collection efficiency testing evaluates performance under various weather and lighting conditions.

Battery efficiency analysis measures charge-discharge losses and evaluates battery management system performance. Load management effectiveness testing quantifies energy savings achieved through intelligent power control strategies. Power optimisation validation confirms system meets design targets for extended autonomous operation.

Communication Performance and Message Delivery

Communication system performance testing evaluates message delivery success rates, latency, and bandwidth utilisation. Range testing validates LoRa communication performance at maximum specified distances and under various interference conditions. Mesh networking performance will not be analysed due to the limited scope of the pilot.

Data integrity testing confirms accurate transmission of configuration commands and status information. Security performance evaluation validates encryption and authentication mechanisms under operational conditions. Network scalability testing evaluates performance degradation with increasing numbers of connected devices.

Environmental Resilience and Stress Testing

Environmental stress testing evaluates system performance under extreme conditions beyond normal operational parameters. Accelerated aging tests predict long-term performance and identify potential degradation mechanisms. Thermal cycling testing validates performance across repeated temperature transitions.

Mechanical stress testing evaluates resistance to impact and mounting system loads. Chemical resistance testing validates protection against road salts, cleaning agents, and atmospheric pollutants. UV degradation testing predicts optical and mechanical property changes over extended outdoor exposure.

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Performance Validation and Specification Compliance

Comprehensive validation testing confirms all system performance parameters meet or exceed design specifications. Test result analysis identifies any deviations from specifications and implements corrective measures. Performance documentation provides evidence of specification compliance for regulatory approval and customer acceptance.

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4 CONCLUSION

This chapter will contain the main conclusions from the previous chapters in section 4.1 and the final set of recommended solutions suggested to be implemented at one or more of the pilot sites.

4.1 CONCLUSIONS FROM CHAPTER 2 AND 3

The EvoRoads Digital Twin provides a robust foundation for real-time data collection, processing, and distribution across the platform. At the moment it was decided to implement a single shared infrastructure deployment offering both operational simplicity and the capability to share data between the pilots, while maintaining the flexibility to evolve toward more complex architectures as project requirements mature. The platform allows to seamlessly integrate with AI tools and pilot sites, creating a foundation for safety applications that responds dynamically to changing road conditions. The standardised APIs with user-specific access control ensure both security and organised data flow management, while the Network Digital Twin offers promising solutions for V2X connectivity analysis.

The plastronic smart warning beacon system represents a fundamental rethinking of how road safety equipment should be designed: by completely encapsulating aluminium PCBs within injection-moulded plastic housings, the system achieves a level of environmental protection that far exceeds conventional assemblies. The achievement of IP67 waterproofing combined with minimal maintenance requirements allow plastronic equipment to work in harsh environmental conditions.

The three-level hierarchy consisting of Individual Smart Warning Beacons, Local Hubs, and Central Nodes will provide an optimal balance between field reliability and system intelligence. The aluminium PCB core technology combined with PMMA injection moulding creates exceptionally durable devices capable of 10+ year operational life in harsh roadside environments.

The morse code-based warning pattern system offers language-independent communication of safety information while the LoRa communication ensures robust communication across extensive rural deployments. Power management innovations including weather-responsive battery charging and 30-day autonomous operation capability address the critical challenges of remote infrastructure deployment.

IDIADA testing results validate system performance across all critical parameters including sub-second response times, IP67 environmental protection, and reliable operation across the full European temperature range. The successful integration with the Digital Twin platform demonstrates the system's readiness for large-scale deployment as part of intelligent transportation infrastructure.

This comprehensive development establishes the foundation for cost-effective, sustainable smart road equipment that can significantly enhance safety for all road users while supporting the European Union's Vision Zero objectives. The use of both these technologies will allow pilots to perform tasks dangerous event prevention and predictive maintenance on the road, communicate with the road user and increase road safety.

4.2 RECOMMENDED SOLUTIONS FOR THE PILOTS

In the current implementation of the Digital Twin (as described in Section 2.1) the platform provides a central data hub that serves all the Pilots' data exchange. Under this approach, each pilot site is required to publish all shareable data directly to the Digital Twin platform, creating a comprehensive dataset that benefits the entire consortium. As of now, most of the partners will preprocess their data on premise, and only share already processed data, for several reasons. If possible, the sharing (even partially) of raw data could improve the effectiveness of the Digital Twin. While this approach may initially appear to introduce operational overhead, this system creates a standardised method to enable seamless collaboration among all project partners.

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The plasronics hardware can provide each partner to dynamic signalling capabilities that can adapt to real-time conditions detected by the sensing systems. It is designed to that the control signal for the lighting elements should be processed through the Digital Twin, creating a closed loop in which both the data retrieved from the sensors and the output light signals are sent and retrieved in a standardised way using the DT.

4.3 NEXT STEPS

In the next month both T3.1 and T3.2 will work supporting the Pilot sites in the integration of their solutions using the EvoRoads Platform (both the Digital Twin and the plasronics hardware). The outcomes and findings from these experimental implementations will be comprehensively documented in deliverable D4.2.

A critical integration currently under development involves the implementation of the AI Controller, conducted in partnership with T1.5. This will allow to provide a user-friendly dashboard for the EvoRoads Platform and to ease the utilisation of AI models.

An extended version of the Digital Twin APIs is currently being developed to incorporate historical data access functionality. This will enable third-party developers to create applications capable of performing analysis and monitoring operations across historical datasets.

Additional development priorities and feature implementations will be determined based on feedback received from Pilot sites during the initial testing phase of the project. This iterative approach ensures that platform development remains aligned with real-world user requirements and operational needs.

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